

Table 2. Effect of leaf pruning on yield and yield components of rice. Cuttack, India, 1995.

Treatment	Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	Panicle weight (g)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Panicle sterility (%)
<i>Variety</i>					
Panidhan	141	2.61	2.3	7.9	8.4
LPR312	151	2.55	2.3	7.2	8.2
CD (5%)	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
<i>Pruning</i>					
No pruning	160	2.73	2.6	10.2	5.5
<i>One pruning at</i>					
80 DAG	148	2.60	2.5	9.6	6.5
100 DAG	138	2.84	2.5	8.6	7.3
120 DAG	143	2.21	2.0	8.6	8.5
<i>Two prunings at</i>					
80 + 100 DAG	143	2.36	2.3	7.7	8.3
100 + 120 DAG	133	2.23	2.0	7.6	8.7
80 + 120 DAG	136	2.16	1.9	7.1	8.3
CD(5%)	12	ns	0.4	1.6	1.1

Early pruning produced more grain yield than delayed pruning. In general, foliage pruning up to 100 DAG produced grain yield comparable with that of no pruning, but pruning thereafter reduced grain yield.

Significant reduction was also found in straw yield at maturity. It was more pronounced when foliage was removed twice. One early pruning (80 DAG) had no adverse effect on straw yield. Pruning delayed after 80 DAG or

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twice at either of the two growth stages reduced straw yield by 19-21% and 33-44% respectively, compared with no pruning.

The results suggest that foliage pruning of tall and long-duration rice variety may be used to supplement cattle rations in lowland areas lacking fodder in wet season. However, foliage should be removed at early growth stages, preferably 35-40 d before flowering, in order not to adversely affect grain yield. ■

Effect of seed rate, seed density, and nitrogen fertilizer on performance of flood-prone lowland rice

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We conducted two experiments during 1994 at Cuttack, India in adjoining fields. In the first, seeds of varying densities were sown at different rates using a common basal dose of 40 kg N ha⁻¹. Nine treatment combinations were arranged in a factorial randomized complete block design with three replications. In experiment 2, only low- and high-density seeds were grown at 400 and 600 seeds m⁻² using 0 and 40 kg N ha⁻¹. Sixteen treatment combinations were arranged in a split-plot design with three replications, keeping submergence levels in main plots and combinations of seed rate, seed density, and N fertilizer in sub-plots.

Rain began 10 d after sowing, with 10.4, 4.8, and 0.8 mm falling at 2-d

Table 1. Growth and yield of rice as influenced by seed rate and seed density in the flood-prone lowlands of Cuttack, India, during 1994 (Experiment 1).^a

Treatment	Seedling emergence (%)	Plant height at maturity (cm)	Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	Panicle weight (g)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)
<i>20 seeds m⁻²</i>						
19.4 mg	30.4	132	75	2.95	2.0	5.6
21.2 mg	32.2	138	107	3.22	2.7	6.0
22.9 mg	33.1	139	115	3.20	2.9	6.7
<i>40 seeds m⁻²</i>						
19.4 mg	30.4	132	93	2.75	2.3	7.8
21.2 mg	32.7	138	116	2.80	2.7	8.3
22.9 mg	33.5	138	122	2.88	2.8	8.7
<i>600 seeds m⁻²</i>						
19.4 mg	30.3	133	106	2.75	2.5	7.9
21.2 mg	32.6	135	127	2.74	2.8	8.6
22.9 mg	34.0	138	121	2.85	2.8	8.2
Mean effects						
<i>Seed rate (m²)</i>						
200	31.9	136	99	3.12	2.5	6.1
400	32.2	136	110	2.81	2.6	8.3
600	32.3	135	118	2.78	2.7	8.2
<i>Seed density (mg)</i>						
19.4	30.4	132	91	2.82	2.3	7.1
21.2	32.5	138	117	2.92	2.7	7.6
22.9	33.5	137	119	2.98	2.8	7.9
CD (P=0.05)						
Seed rate	ns	ns	ns	0.25	ns	0.83
Seed density	ns	3	ns	ns	0.2	ns
Interaction	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.4	ns

^a Gayatri, a semidwarf, long-duration, photoperiod-sensitive, relatively flood-tolerant variety, was used. Crop was direct-sown on 25 May after premonsoon showers at a row spacing of 20 cm using a common basal dose of 8.7 kg P ha⁻¹ and 16.7 kg K ha⁻¹. Seeds of varying grades were obtained by repeated screening of thoroughly cleaned seeds in a saline solution (sp. gr., 1.2; 300 g common salt L⁻¹ of water).

Table 2. Growth and yield of rice as influenced by seed rate (A), seed density (B), and N fertilizer (C) under natural submergence (S1) and simulated flashflooding (S2) at Cuttack, India, during 1994 (Experiment 2).

Treatment	Seedling emergence (%)	Plant height (cm)		Panicles m ⁻² (no.)		Panicle weight (g)		Grain yield (tha ⁻¹)		Straw yield (tha ⁻¹)	
		S1	S2	S1	S2	S1	S2	S1	S2	S1	S2
Seed rate (m ⁻²)											
400	32.3	125	112	77	67	2.88	2.16	2.5	1.7	4.7	2.7
600	30.9	129	113	82	79	2.71	2.08	2.4	1.9	5.4	3.0
Seed density (mg)											
19.4	29.8	126	112	74	68	2.53	2.07	2.3	1.6	4.9	2.4
22.9	33.4	128	113	85	78	3.06	2.17	2.5	1.9	5.3	3.2
N fertilizer (kg ha ⁻¹)											
0	31.5	125	107	76	64	2.68	2.02	2.2	1.6	4.4	2.3
40	3.18	129	118	83	82	2.91	2.27	2.6	2.0	5.6	3.2
Mean	-	127	111	80	73	2.80	2.10	2.4	1.8	5.0	2.8
CD (0.05)											
Submergence level			13		ns		1		0.33		2.05
Mean effects of A, B, or C	3.0		5		5		2		1		1
Interaction (S X A, B, or C) ^b			6		7		7		0.15		2

^a Same variety and natural conditions as in Table 1. Simulated flashflooding was done in especially constructed tanks at 90±2 cm depth for 10 d continuously at 75 d of growth. ^b Interaction between A, B, and C was not significant.

intervals during the second week of June. These conditions resulted in delayed and very poor germination (<35%). Seedling emergence 25 d after sowing was significantly higher in high-density seeds, but percent emergence from different seed rates or N fertilizer levels were similar (Tables 1 and 2).

Plants raised from dense seeds appeared more vigorous and suffered less from the initial drought. Water built up from the last week of June and rose rapidly to 30 cm at 18 d after seedling emergence (DE) and 70 cm at 34 DE. Subsequent flooding completely submerged plants for about a week. However, the relatively taller and vigorous rice plants raised from high-density seeds and with N fertilizer application showed better recovery after the flood receded. Natural flooding up to 82 cm at the end of August also submerged most plants for more than 10 d. Experiment 2 also subjected the crop to simulated flashflooding at the beginning of September for 10 d, after which the floodwater receded gradually.

At crop maturity, the plants from high-density seeds were taller, but seed rates made no significant difference (Table 1). Artificial flashflooding re-

duced plant height significantly more than natural submergence (Table 2). The ability of N fertilizer to increase plant height was more pronounced under flashflooding conditions.

In experiment 1, mean grain yield remained unaffected by increased seed rate because an increase in number of panicles m⁻² at a higher seed rate was associated with reduced panicle weight (Table 1). Interaction comparison revealed that yield increased significantly with increasing seed density, particularly at the lower seed rates of 200 and 400 seeds m⁻². Grain yield increased up to 600 seeds m⁻² with the use of low-density seeds, but the effect from using medium- and high-density seeds at varying rates was similar. This result suggests that seed rate can be reduced by using high-density seeds. Vigorous seedlings not only establish well but survive better under drought or flooding; also, plants compensate for the poor crop stand at the lower seed rate through increased tillering.

In experiment 2, the beneficial effects of seed rate, seed density, and N fertilizer were more pronounced under simulated flashflooding than under natural submergence (Table 2). The mean increase in yield from N fertilizer, high-density seeds, and higher seed

rate was 25.2, 20.9, and 11.8%, respectively under simulated flashflooding conditions. Higher seed rate did not affect yield under natural submergence, but instead yield increased by 15.7 and 8.7% using N fertilizer and high-density seeds. The greater beneficial effect of N and high-density seeds was associated with a greater number and weight of panicles. Mean grain yield decreased 25.7% by flashflooding compared with natural submergence, but similar reductions in yield were less with the use of 40 kg N ha⁻¹ (22.9%), high-density seeds (21.6%), and higher seed rate (19.9%) than without N (28.7%), low-density seed (29.9%), and normal seed rate (30.4%), respectively.

We conclude that yield performance of flood-prone lowland rice depends largely on initial crop stand and vigor, which can be improved by using a higher seed rate and plump seeds with basal fertilization. High-density seeds germinate better and produce vigorous seedlings, leading to greater survival under initial drought and flashflooding. These abiotic stresses can also be mitigated by increasing the seed rate and N fertilizer. ■

Effect of tillage and fertilizer levels on grain yield and incidence of brown spot disease in rice

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This study was done in kharif 1992 and 1993 at Pantnagar to observe the effect of tillage practices and fertilizer levels on rice production and disease incidence. A split-plot design was used with puddled 'P' and unpuddled 'UP' as main plots and two fertilizer levels as subplots of 11.8 × 6.0 m. Fertilizer levels were F₁: 120 kg N ha⁻¹, 17 kg P ha⁻¹, and